

PERSPECTIVE OPEN ACCESS

When the Wind Blows: Exposing the Constraints of Drone-Based Environmental Mapping

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Correspondence: Jan Komárek (komarekjan@fzp.czu.cz)**Received:** 18 February 2025 | **Revised:** 25 March 2025 | **Accepted:** 27 March 2025**Funding:** The author received no specific funding for this work.**Keywords:** aerial data distortion | drone limits | weather dependency

ABSTRACT

Drones have become indispensable for high-resolution, on-demand remote sensing, yet their valid operational window is far narrower than often portrayed. Using meteorological data from 31 locations in the Czech Republic since 2016, we demonstrate that weather constraints—including precipitation, wind and temperature extremes—collectively limit feasible flight days to roughly 25% per year. Although an overall 0.8°C rise in average temperature since 2019 has slightly reduced cold-weather issues, it has introduced more frequent heatwaves and increased wind variability, offsetting potential gains. High wind gusts, precipitation and temperature can degrade sensor accuracy and distort imagery even when conditions permit flight. Radiometric data collection—often conducted near solar noon—can be disrupted by clouds, haze or gusts, complicating efforts to obtain consistent, high-quality measurements. Despite these pervasive effects, many drone-based studies lack detailed weather documentation, hindering data reproducibility and comparisons. Weather nowcasting and adaptive mission planning offer ways to mitigate data gaps, but questions remain about ensuring sustained, high-quality coverage in variable climates. By acknowledging and addressing inherent weather constraints, the remote sensing community can more realistically harness drones' potential and refine operational guidelines for long-term environmental monitoring.

Highlights: Meteorological constraints are a strong reality check.

Climate trends alter but don't solve drone limitations.

Future improvements must go beyond hardware enhancements.

The rise of drone technology has led to more studies highlighting its advantages over traditional remote sensing platforms. Drones are recognised for their high-resolution data acquisition, cost efficiency, on-demand operability, and ability to be deployed virtually anywhere (Hardin et al. 2019; Manfreda et al. 2018). Unlike satellites, which capture data consistently regardless of surface conditions, precipitation, strong winds or extreme temperatures can significantly constrain drone operation and their data [1, 2]. If drones are regarded as a reliable complement or substitute

for traditional remote sensing, their operational feasibility across different climate zones must be critically examined. This article presents real-world drone operability using meteorological data from 31 locations across the Czech Republic and discusses the implications for environmental remote sensing applications from 2016. Additionally, it extends the analysis to include updated meteorological data through 2024, assessing whether recent climatic trends have substantially influenced drone usability.

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FIGURE 1 | Methodological pipeline of assessing weather conditions.

TABLE 1 | Averaged number of days exceeding weather conditions (C₁–C₆) across all spots and years.

	Conditions—daily limits	Threshold	No. of days exceeding condition	% significance of conditions
C ₁	Precipitation	≤ 1 mm	145	30
C ₂	Temperature means	≥ 5 °C	51	11
C ₃	Temperature means (no precipitation)	≥ -5 °C	8	2
C ₄	Wind means	≤ 5 m s ⁻¹	35	7
C ₅	Wind max	≤ 8 m s ⁻¹	226	47
C ₆	Temperature max	≤ 30 °C	17	3

In contrast to the widely held belief in near-universal drone deployability, their ability to acquire valuable data is subject to significant constraints. Our analysis of available meteorological data since 2016 suggests a starkly different reality when data is a priority; see Figure 1 and Table 1 for the conditions. Drones obtaining data (e.g., imagery, lidar) are not designed for operation in any precipitation, as moisture can damage

electronic components, obscure optical sensors, and distort acquired data. On average, precipitation exceeded operational limits in 30%–44% of days per year, significantly restricting flight opportunities; condition details are tabulated below. Wind gusts exceeding 8–10 m s⁻¹, frequently observed in open landscapes and mountainous terrains, can substantially impede stable drone operation, affecting up to 38% of potential flight windows. In

addition, gusts and localised turbulence in urban canyons (wind tunnels), forest edges or ridge lines can induce sudden instability, culminating in mission failures. Temperature is also critical in drone operability, affecting battery performance and sensor accuracy. Low temperatures can lead to rapid battery drainage, reduced lift and increased risk of ice formation on propellers. Subzero temperatures affected drone usability on 15% of days per year. High temperatures risk overheating onboard electronics and reducing battery efficiency. Drones often have recommended operational ranges of -10°C – 40°C , meaning extreme summer and winter conditions can further restrict usability. As a result, the realistic operational window for drone-based remote sensing in Central European conditions is limited to approximately 90–110 days per year, depending on the data source (NASA, CHMI). The average percentage of days convenient for systematic data collection is $24.5\% \pm 7.5\%$ across tested 31 spots over 2016–2019.

We further compared meteorological data from 2020 to 2024 with previous datasets to assess whether climate variability has affected drone usability. The average annual temperature in the Czech Republic has risen by 0.8°C since 2019, slightly reducing the number of subzero days. However, more frequent heatwaves have introduced new constraints, particularly in mid-summer months. Wind speeds have shown more significant fluctuations, with a 5% increase in days exceeding 8 m s^{-1} compared to 2016–2019. The number of days with excessive precipitation remains unchanged, reinforcing previous drone usability estimates. Although climate trends suggest slightly fewer cold-weather limitations, the increase in wind intensity and summer heatwaves offsets these gains, keeping overall drone operability relatively stable.

1 | Beyond the Hype

Weather conditions determine whether a drone can be deployed and directly affect the quality and reliability of the data obtained. Drone resistance to wind and precipitation and optimising flight trajectories may be overcome by tuning the hardware or software [3, 4]; nevertheless, meteorological phenomena still affect wireless signal propagation and thus drone communication capabilities [5, 6]. Considering the sensor and desired data, distortion will be propagated despite optimised platform performance. Strong winds, often increasing around midday, impact drone flight stability, leading to potential motion blur and misalignment in captured images. Even if the weather is clear, excessive turbulence may result in motion blur or distorted orthorectification and georeferencing due to unstable flight paths. At the same time, precipitation, fog, low cloud ceilings or high humidity can interfere with sensor performance, reduce visibility and distort optical data due to moisture accumulation on a sensor. Water droplets on the onboard sensor can scatter light and create artefacts in imagery, rendering data unusable. Temperature extremes can degrade battery life and onboard electronics, necessitating more frequent landings and interrupting data collection. Temperature peaks may also reduce thermal sensors' efficiency.

Despite these influences, many studies employing drone-based remote sensing omit or provide limited information regarding the prevailing weather conditions. Such omissions make it difficult

to replicate experiments or compare findings across different projects, ultimately hindering efforts to develop standardised best practices for drone deployments in environmental research, especially when sensor synergies are considered [7]. Radiometric accuracy is crucial in drone-based remote sensing, particularly multispectral and hyperspectral imaging. Although solar noon, when the Sun provides the highest and most stable light intensity, ensures strong reflectance signals, weather conditions significantly affect the quality and usability of data collected. Shadows distort radiometric measurements, particularly in complex terrain. Thus, the near-nadir solar angle may minimise these effects. If repeated drone flights are scheduled to cover potential environmental changes over time, acquiring data at a consistent solar angle may ensure comparability. On the other hand, solar noon does not always guarantee optimal drone operations, as weather conditions can significantly degrade radiometric data quality and even prevent flights entirely. Clouds and haze may scatter sunlight, reducing direct illumination and altering surface reflectance properties, and thus may produce radiometrically inconsistent results.

2 | Conclusion

Drones are powerful remote sensing tools for obtaining airborne data in detailed resolution. Such weather constraints, however, raise critical questions about their role in long-term environmental monitoring. As this perspective highlights, their real-world usability is significantly constrained by meteorological conditions, making them far less omnipresent than often claimed. Although technological advancements in battery efficiency, wind resistance and waterproofing may extend operational limits, current sensor technology and data-obtaining approaches remain heavily dependent on favourable weather. Although solar noon remains the gold standard for drone radiometric data collection, weather conditions impose significant constraints that must be managed. A flexible approach to flight scheduling and real-time weather adaptation is crucial to ensuring high-quality remote sensing outputs.

Recent advances in UAV hardware miniaturisation, sensor integration and flight-planning automation have substantially broadened the operational scope of drone-based environmental research (Nex et al. 2022). Despite these technological strides, the local climate remains a defining factor in mission feasibility, data completeness and sensor reliability. The intersection between cutting-edge drone hardware and real-world meteorological constraints underpins the need for integrated planning, contingency measures and thorough weather documentation—factors critical for expanding drone use into emerging domains, such as beyond visual line-of-sight operations, persistent multi-sensor and fleet monitoring setups and hybrid approaches combining various sensors and platforms offering the best balance between resolution and temporal continuity. We must account for these limitations to avoid unrealistic expectations in drone-based monitoring, where systematic, high-quality data acquired are expected. Overstating drone availability risks undermining their actual applicability and long-term reliability. By recognising and addressing these constraints, the remote sensing community can develop drone applications, ensuring their potential is maximised within the bounds of meteorological reality.

Future research should focus on refining mission-planning software through advanced, AI-driven weather prediction models to optimise drone deployment schedules better. Adaptive go and no-go geo-fencing approaches based on nowcasting may be integrated into the control and planning software. Moreover, real-time weather monitoring and drone automation may adjust flight altitudes and routes to maintain data integrity. Another key direction involves comparative studies in diverse climates to build a global perspective on drone operability and resilience. Additionally, advancements in dehazing drone imagery are essential to mitigate atmospheric distortions caused by fog, haze and dust, which degrade image clarity and spectral accuracy. Developing robust dehazing algorithms, particularly leveraging deep learning [8] and multi-sensor fusion, will enhance data quality, ensuring reliable analysis in challenging weather conditions. Collectively, these efforts would provide robust guidelines for drone deployments across various environmental conditions.

Author Contributions

Jan Komárek: conceptualisation, writing original draft preparation, visualisation.

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Ethical Statement

The authors have nothing to report.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in the SoDa service at <https://www.soda-pro.com> and the CHMI service at <https://www.chmi.cz>.

Peer Review

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